

Recommended citation: Damiani, E. M. (2021). How to Add Innovation and Design into Introductory Electrical Engineer Classes. In Heiß, H.-U., Järvinen, H.-M., Mayer, A., & Schulz, A. (Eds.), *Blended Learning in Engineering Education: challengingm enlightening and lasting? SEFI 49th Annual Conference* (pp. 794-803). European Society for Engineering Education (SEFI), Berlin, Germany. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.14650269.

HOW TO ADD INNOVATION AND DESIGN INTO INTRODUCTORY ELECTRICAL ENGINEERING CLASSES

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Conference Key Areas: *Engineering Skills, Curriculum Development, Engineering teaching*

Keywords: *Curriculum, Design, Electrical, Projects*

ABSTRACT

It is becoming more commonly acknowledged that effective methods for educating engineers is through active learning strategies such as Design Projects. What is more challenging is developing these active strategies that are focused on broader accessibility, participation, and inclusion. This curriculum development paper will describe specific activities, design projects, and strategies that have been developed and revised in introductory Electrical Engineering classes. The projects develop engineering competence through students utilizing technical concepts, analytical reasoning, practical skills and professional judgement to solve open-ended design problems. All activities place priority on student experience and competency development as compared to a faculty centric approach.

INTRODUCTION

To develop the engineering student of today into the engineer that we will need tomorrow it is vital to build a curriculum that is relevant, applied, challenging and inspires students to apply the knowledge to new and different applications [1, 2]. To accomplish this it is important to shift some of the current curriculum focus away from traditional lecture format. A pair of studies from 2005 by Shuman [3] and Loui [4] focused on the ineffectiveness of the traditional lecture format for teaching ABET professional skills and argued that a modern engineering education should focus on active and cooperative learning approaches. Sheppard adds, "In the Engineering Science and technology courses, the tradition of putting theory before practice and the effort to cover technical knowledge comprehensively, allow little opportunity for students to have the kind of deep learning experiences that mirror professional practice and problem solving" [1]. Rather than focusing strictly on theory and technical laws, engineering education needs to broaden its scope and include curriculum that develops the spirit and the professional practice that we are also seeking [2].

Goldberg offers some guiding questions to consider in improving Engineering education:

- 1) How do we produce the innovators that are needed for our times?
- 2) How do we inspire students to become intrinsically motivated to learn?
- 3) How do teachers step down off the stage and involve themselves as coaches inside and outside the classroom?
- 4) How do we renew the culture of engineering education to make it relevant, creative and fulfilling? [2]

Engineering is inherently a creative enterprise. While scientists ask “Why?” engineers must ask “why not?” Engineers are responsible for imagining what has never been and then doing whatever it takes to bring visions to reality. In the fundamental sense, “to engineer” is “to make.” Making requires more than the analytical mind. It also requires the design mind [2].

Design is widely considered to be the central or distinguishing activity of engineering [5]. It has also long been said that engineering programs should graduate engineers who can design effective solutions to meet social needs [6]. Despite these facts, the role of design in engineering education remains largely as stated by Evans, “The subject of design seems to occupy the top drawer of a Pandora’s Box of controversial curriculum matters, a box often opened only as accreditation time approaches. Even ‘design’ faculty—those often segregated from ‘analysis’ faculty by the courses they teach—have trouble articulating this elusive creature called design” [7, 8].

Design is hard to learn and harder still to teach [8]. Cobb states the term design-based learning has been broadly applied across the many fields of Science [9]. In a 2002 study Edelson defines design as open-ended, reflective and relying on creativity. He goes on to state, “In Challenging or innovative design, decisions can be complex, interdependent, requiring extensive investigation, experimentation and iterative refinement on the part of the designers. In these cases, the designers inevitably acquire substantial new understanding.”[10]. Design faculty across the country and across a range of educational institutions still feel that the leaders of engineering departments and schools are unable or unwilling to recognize the intellectual complexities and resources demanded to support good design education [11].

This author’s journey down the path of adding more design to the curriculum started with the desire to better engage students in the enjoyment of a real metacognitive challenge, the kind of challenge only attained by a true open-ended engineering design project. Initially, concern was for asking too much of the students and the potential for a failed experiment. Maybe an 18-20 year-old student wouldn’t have the maturity, creativity and drive to overcome the many challenges they would face. I couldn’t have been more wrong! Right from the start the students impressed me with how much they embraced the idea of getting to create something. It was as if they had been waiting for me to wake up and finally give them a real engineering challenge! It’s been over 15 years now with steadily increasing complexity of projects, and the students have never disappointed in their ability to rise to the

challenge. In fact, many times student prevailed with better solutions than their instructor. What follows is a description of four projects that have been used in the introductory electrical engineering sequence of classes.

The projects are presented in the order that this author typically uses them. In the development of electrical comprehension, as with most areas of engineering, it is vital that the concepts are presented in such an order that it promotes student understanding. In the study of electricity it is also important to build a basic understanding, comfort and belief that electricity makes sense and can be predictable. The first project presented, the battery project, is not a design project. It is however, a great project for a student's first electrical class that builds a strong foundation for future design work.

THE DESIGN PROJECTS

Battery Project – Physics 2 Class

A group of students is given 7 to 8 different AA batteries and asked to determine which battery is the “Best Bang for the Buck”. Instruction is given on how to measure battery capacity in ma-hr. A visit to a leading battery manufacturer's website will help to answer some questions (Energizer.com has a nice technical info section link at the bottom of the home page). This research will reveal how critical discharge rate is to determining battery capacity. This instructor uses an average discharge rate of 200 mA. This is a good average discharge rate and will allow for the discharge to be done within a reasonable 8 -12 hours of data taking. For 1.5 volt AA batteries, a good size resistor to use to attain a 200 mA discharge rate is 4.7 ohms. Students' record voltage every half hour until battery voltage is below 0.8 volts, the industry standard. The voltage data is then put in to a spreadsheet program to graph volt vs time and current vs time. The students find the area under the mA vs hours graph then divide the area by the cost per battery. This will give them mAhr/\$ or energy per dollar, “Bang for the Buck”.

The batteries should be purchased locally and purchased in the largest package available to attain the lowest price per battery. Purchase an assortment of battery chemistries like lithium, manganese dioxide (alkaline) and zinc chloride. This will give more interesting results and also show students the significance of the Chemistry involved. It is also educational to add on a few extra questions pertaining to batteries. Questions like: How does temperature affect battery performance? What is battery memory? What are some recent battery developments? How can I tell how much energy is left in a battery? Does discharge rate effect overall battery capacity? How do Alkaline, NiMH, Ni-Cd and Li ion batteries compare?

This project tends to be a great introductory electrical experiment. It answers a very relevant question, “What is the best battery?” It builds confidence with electricity and provides opportunity for practice with a voltmeter. The project also puts students in groups to learn from each other, helps to clarify the difference between current, voltage, energy and power (four concepts that students often confuse), lets students use a spreadsheet and apply basic Calculus in a real-world problem. All of this helps to build a solid foundation which prepares them to succeed in future classes.

Circuit to Meet a Need in Society - Circuits 1 Class

For this project students are given the very open-ended task of building a circuit to meet a need in society. Grading is based on originality of need met, difficulty of circuit design, creativity of solution and quality of manufacturing.

The first two weeks of the class are very lab intensive. Students learn and build many different types of electrical circuits with an assortment of devices and sensors that will become the components of their final project. Each of the concepts taught connect and build upon the previous concepts. The circuits, devices and sensors taught include astable and monostable circuits, 555 timer, pulse-width modulation (PWM) circuits, servo-motors, potentiometers, photoresistors, thermistors, transistors, photo-transistors, hall-effect sensors, infrared detectors, relays ... etc. Preliminary challenges are assigned during the first two weeks to ensure students can build the circuits applying all of the devices and sensors. Challenges may include set off an alarm to trip on increasing darkness/brightness, trip on lowering/rising temperature or trip when a laser beam is broken.

This design project provides a number of significant benefits for student learning. Students are learning many new electrical concepts and applications. Students are learning how to apply technical solutions to a real world design where they actually have to build the solution. Students also have to, maybe for the first time, find their own problem to solve. Often in a class the instructor chooses the problem to solve; design a bridge, build a windmill...etc. This design project however, asks the student to assess their environment and find the problem to solve themselves. This methodology takes student learning and involvement to a whole new level. The student is no longer a passive member in their own education but are beginning to discover problems and direct their own solutions. This is the very essence of engineering, recognizing a need, evaluating the need, applying technical knowledge to resolve the need, thus improving society.

The open-ended nature of this project allows students to push their limits of creativity and to more effectively learn circuits through genuine application of the concepts. Students often achieve a high level of personal accomplishment and take a great deal of pride in their project. This project results in a wide spectrum of products such as ice fishing tip-up alarms, laser activated burglar alarms, light follow circuits for solar panels, automatic cat feeders, entertaining games of skill with flashing lights and buzzers... the list goes on and on. Students are given six weeks for this project.

Fig 1: Laser beam protected Jewelry box alarm.

Fig 2: Salt dispensing snow shovel.

Submarine Flood Alarm Project – Digital Logic Class

The earlier part of this author's life was served on a submarine. So this project is modeled after the flood alarm system found onboard a naval submarine. The project is pitched to the students as a government contract their company is trying to win. The contract is to design a flood alarm system that will be used on all Navy and Coast Guard ships to be operated in saltwater and freshwater. Students are to design, build and test all physical and electrical components. The alarm system is to include a caution alarm and a danger alarm. The caution alarm activates at a lower water level. The alarm system requires both a loud auditory alarm and a flashing yellow light. It should also have a cutout switch which will silence the auditory alarm but also line up a circuit to sound the auditory alarm again if the cutout switch is still activated after the water level has lowered. The danger alarm activates at a higher water level but all of the other features are exactly the same as the caution alarm. This helps provide the redundancy required for any piece of safety equipment on a naval ship.

At the start of this project students are taught the basic logic gates (inverter, And, Or, Nand, Nor, Xor, Xnor). They are encouraged to use these gates to solve this problem. They will also have to use past knowledge to build the 555 astable circuits to drive the auditory alarms and the flashing lights. For the design of the actual flood sensor they are given a 5 gallon bucket along with Styrofoam, wood dowels, aluminum foil, steel washers, PVC piping and wire. Students are encouraged to build their own switches for this project. Switches can be easily built using the supplies provided. Students will need to be taught how to use pull-up and pull-down resistors to send a high or low when a switch is open or closed.

This project provides a very student centered way to teach logic gates. Often the process of learning digital logic gates involves more of an exercise in memorization and a quiz. This project forces students to think about problem needs and how and which combination of logic gates could match those requirements. In addition, students are required to build their own sensor. The problem of measuring water level will require students to figure out how to change a rising float into an electrical

voltage than can be understood by a digital logic chip. This project also requires students to recall old knowledge and combine it with new knowledge to solve a very open ended problem. The 555 timer circuit in astable configuration will need to be applied to create the alarm tone and the flashing LEDs.

Grading is based on reliability of operation and creativity of circuit and flotation construction. Each group is asked to present and explain their circuit operation for the class. Students are given one week for this project.

Fig 3: Flotation system

Fig 4: Flotation and circuit

Fig 5: Submarine alarm circuit

Motor Design Project - Circuits II

Students are to design, build and test either a DC motor or a brushless motor. They are given magnets, magnetic wire, copper tubing, wood, steel rod and access to 3D-printers, laser cutters and a machine shop. Prior to the project students are taught concepts of DC motor and brushless motor operation including magnetism, split ring commutators, brushes, electronic speed controllers and 3 phase generation.

Students are given the opportunity to reverse engineer a number of manufactured motors. This allows them to see a number of different designs, appreciate quality manufacturing and to learn what has already been done in motor design. It is important to supply students with quality magnets either neodymium magnets or industrial size and strength magnets. Good quality magnets will more easily allow students to have success even if their rotor winding tolerances are not very good. It is valuable to maintain a few student motors from previous years. This seems to result in steady improvement in student designs from year-to-year. The students benefit from the larger sized three dimensional example to help them visualize their own projects. Evaluation is based on the creativity of design, quality of manufacturing and the maximum RPM attained by their motor. Students are given 6 weeks for the project.

The author has only been using this design project for about 3 years, but what is truly inspiring is how many of the students will try to improve on manufactured motor design. Their quality of production may not be quite as good as a store bought motor but they will often push themselves to try out new and different ideas than what they have seen in any other motor. The variety, originality and quality of student designs is impressive. It becomes obvious why employers want to hire young engineers - they have endless energy, think differently and don't accept the status-quo.

Fig 6: A few DC motor designs.

Fig 7: A few different brushless motors.

ADDITIONAL THOUGHTS ON DESIGN BASED LEARNING

Design-based projects provide an enhanced opportunity for critical thinking, application of technical concepts, and practical experience. So, it is wise to consider the balance of the project framework. For example, too many constraints may limit how far the student can explore the boundaries. Consequently, students lose the educational benefits of discovering for themselves what the natural limits are. Similarly, if no parameters are imposed, students may lack direction and project

scope. This can significantly impact motivation for the in-experienced student. Furthermore, it is this author's belief, that in the first two years of an engineering education it is important to give students as much personal hands on experience as possible. In the case of a young electrical engineer this time is critical in developing the experience, comfort, conceptual understandings and electrical instincts that will be their foundation for all the electrical concepts that follow. Consequently, with the exception of the battery project, the projects presented here are limited to 1-2 students in a group. This will more guarantee each student has full involvement in the project. In regards to developing the skills of working in a larger group, there is plenty of time to provide these opportunities in the third and fourth years of their education. The emphasize in the first two years needs to be foundational concepts, hands on experience, opportunities to act on their ideas and inspiration in their chosen field of study; best accomplished in the small group environment.

One of the significant outcomes noted in using the design-based projects in electrical engineering classes is the improved ability of students to troubleshoot electrical circuits. The circuits that students are building are complex enough that invariably they will make a wiring error or one of the components will fail. Either way, at some point, usually in Circuits 1, they will have to troubleshoot the problem. Around this time, a short lesson on the fundamentals of troubleshooting is taught. It is a step by step summary of how to narrow down and isolate the problem. It is part Art, part Science to efficiently troubleshoot a circuit. Letting the student struggle to find the problem is beneficial for a while but at some point it is more effective for the instructor to work with the student to demonstrate proper use of test equipment to troubleshoot the problem. One good one-on-one training session is usually all it takes. Then the next time there is a problem, students have the confidence, knowledge and experience to figure it out on their own. The process has been very effective at developing one of a young engineer's most valuable skills, the ability to troubleshoot a problem!

Design-based projects take time and balance. Allowing occasional in-class time for working on the project allows the instructor to evaluate the process. Students also want to show their progress and occasionally ask instructor input. This is a normal human characteristic and part of the student's motivational needs. It is important for instructors to provide this access. It also allows you to keep track if students are having any difficulties that you did not anticipate.

A common instructor concern is, "How do you grade projects with the potential for so much variety?" Some instructors would feel most comfortable with a matrix with an itemized list of desired attributes and the appropriate score attached to each level of attainment. For this author the process is arguably more subjective. At the start of the project students are informed that their grade will be based on quality of manufacturing, originality of design ideas, complexity of final circuit design and professionalism of group presentation. This author then relies upon experience to assign the appropriate grade with feedback to the student on positives and negatives of their total design experience. One thing to keep in mind is that no two groups will

be the same. One group may have a fairly simple design but spend a large amount of time and energy creating a very finished project with a high level of manufacturing. Another group may spend their time and creativity solving a much more complex electrical challenge but then not have as a high a quality of manufacturing in their finished project. Both groups benefitted and grew from the experience and in this author's opinion have the potential of still getting high marks. Also keep in mind that with this style of teaching there is often much more learning that occurs than what may be seen in the final project. Be sure to have students share their failures and struggles in their final presentation to the class. As much learning happens through one's failed ideas as during one's successful ideas. Whatever grading scale you decide to impose, the most important thing is that you never let the fear of how you will grade the assignment prevent you from challenging your students with a design project. Your students will thank you for the opportunity!

CONCLUSION

Looking forward, the author intends to survey students to more accurately evaluate success of design based learning. Student feedback will also aid in improving these projects. In addition, sharing these ideas with other professionals should aid in even further improvement. Each of the projects presented here have gone through numerous iterations. Constructing a good design project for students takes time and often takes numerous modifications. Evaluating the success and sustainability of a design project from year-to-year raises several questions:

- 1) What is to be gained by keeping or slightly modifying the current project?
- 2) What is to be gained by establishing a rotation of projects?
- 3) What significant improvements could be gained by more timely observation of student progress as well as student feedback on the difficulties they're facing?

Sheppard's characterization of what engineers do is especially relevant to design based learning: engineers "scope, generate, evaluate, and realize ideas" [6]. This focuses in on how engineers think and embraces the heart of the design process by highlighting the creation, assessment, selection, and the making or bringing to life of ideas[8]. The design- based learning approach provides an opportunity for metacognitive growth and naturally shifts the focus from teacher to student. This provides a catalyst for intrinsic motivation and genuine engineering skill development.

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